

Strain Limited Design in Fiber Reinforced Plastic Pressure Vessel

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ABSTRACT

Strains in a dual laminate fiber reinforced plastic cylindrical vessel are measured when the internal pressure increases up to 0.96 MPa (140 psig). Laminate theory was used successfully in calculating the strains. Reasonable agreement was obtained between experimental and theoretical results. A new formulation is developed to calculate optimal winding angles such that the ratio of strains along different directions is minimum. This would provide efficient strain limited designs.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber glass reinforced plastic laminates have been used extensively for making chemical processing vessels and pipings. This is due to their excellent corrosion resistance and their good strengths. Even though these materials have been used for making vessels for a long time, little effort has been spent in studying their behavior [1]. The ASME Code [2] and the British Standards [3] provide some guidelines for the design of vessels. However, these guidelines are either for vessels made up of hand lay up materials or are sketchy for vessels made up of other constructions. There are vessels that do not contain just hand lay up materials alone and the mechanical behavior of these materials needs studying.

This paper presents the results of a preliminary effort in studying the mechanical behavior of a dual laminate fiber reinforced plastic vessel. The thickness of this vessel consists of a PVC inner lining for leak protection purpose, a layer of hand lay up and a layer of filament winding to provide stiffness and strength (Figure 1). Experimental results show that there is a large difference in the strain values along the hoop direction and the longitudinal direction. Analysis using laminate theory confirms these experimental results. Further analysis shows that even though a winding angle of 54.7° gives a ratio of 2 between strength and longitudinal strength, a different winding angle is required for the strains to be the same in the two directions.

Fig. 1 Normal cross section of the vessel

Fig. 2 Location of gages

EXPERIMENTS

The experiments were performed on a 1.22m (48 inch) inside diameter vessel built by CPF Dualam Ltd., at Montreal. The vessel is 8.26m (27 feet 2 inches) long and is supported horizontally by two saddles 4.5m (14 feet 9 inches) apart. Strain gages were mounted at various locations on the vessel and the vessel was pressurized using water up to a pressure of 0.965 MPa (140 psig). The results of all seventy gages are reported in Reference [4]. Only the typical results obtained from gages #21H and #22A are shown in this paper. The locations of these two gages are shown in Figures 1 and 2. All measurements were made at 18.3° C. The filament winding direction is making an angle of 54.7° with the longitudinal axis. Table 1 shows the results obtained from these gages. The average of two values taken over a 10 minute interval after the pressure is applied is shown. Gage #21H shows the hoop strain and gage #22A shows the axial strain. Figure 3 shows the variation of these strains with the applied pressure. From the results, the following is noted:

- The hoop strain shows an approximately linear variation with the applied pressure.
- The axial strain also increases linearly with the increase in pressure but the rate of increase is very small.
- At the maximum pressure (0.965 MPa), the ratio of hoop strain is very large.

ANALYSIS

Certainly there needs to be a confirmation to the large difference between the strains in the two directions. The erroneous concept that a ratio of 2 between the hoop stress and the longitudinal stress should yield the same ratio between the strains can lead to inefficient designs, especially for brittle materials where the limit on strain can be equally important as the limit on stress. Laminate theory is used in the following analysis to confirm the

results. The loadings that are applied on the vessel are the pressure and the bending due to the weight of water. Loading due to pressure is considered first.

Fig. 3 Variation of strain with pressure

Pressure Loading:

Considering the ratio of thickness over diameter of the vessel $t/D = \frac{3.75\text{cm}}{122\text{cm}} \approx \frac{1}{32}$, the vessel can be analyzed as a thin wall vessel with the average stress in the wall to be given as:

$$\sigma_h = \frac{pr}{t} \quad (1)$$

and $\sigma_a = \frac{pr}{2t} \quad (2)$

where p is the pressure, r is the radius and t is the thickness.

The stress therefore can be assumed to be the same over each of the constituent layer of the vessel. For the filament winding layer where the strains were measured, the strain-stress relationship can be written as [5]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \epsilon_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} & \bar{S}_{12} & \bar{S}_{16} \\ \bar{S}_{12} & \bar{S}_{22} & \bar{S}_{26} \\ \bar{S}_{16} & \bar{S}_{26} & \bar{S}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{S}_{11} &= S_{11} \cos^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \sin^2\theta + S_{22} \sin^4\theta \\ \bar{S}_{12} &= S_{12} (\sin^4\theta + \cos^4\theta) + (S_{11} + S_{22} - S_{66}) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta \\ \bar{S}_{22} &= S_{12} \sin^4\theta + (2S_{12} + S_{66}) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + S_{22} \cos^4\theta \\ \bar{S}_{16} &= (2S_{11} - 2S_{12} - S_{66}) \sin\theta \cos^3\theta - (2S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66}) \sin^3\theta \cos\theta \\ \bar{S}_{26} &= (2S_{11} - 2S_{12} - S_{66}) \sin^3\theta \cos\theta - (2S_{22} - 2S_{12} - S_{66}) \sin\theta \cos^3\theta \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4: Coordinate Transformation

$$\bar{S}_{66} = 2(S_{11} + 2S_{22} - 4S_{12} - S_{66}) \sin^2\theta \cos^2\theta + S_{66} (\sin^4\theta + \cos^4\theta)$$

where the $S_{11} - S_{66}$ are defined in terms of the engineering constants as:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{11} &= \frac{1}{E_1} \\ S_{12} &= -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_1} = -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_2} \\ S_{22} &= \frac{1}{E_2} \\ S_{66} &= \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where E's are Young's moduli, ν 's are Poisson ratios, and G is shear modulus. In case of the filament wound layer where the alternate layers make equal angles to the x axis, assuming that the numbers of alternate layers are the same, it can be shown that $\bar{S}_{16} = \bar{S}_{26} = 0$ and equation (3) can be written as:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon_x \\ \epsilon_y \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{S}_{11} & \bar{S}_{12} & 0 \\ \bar{S}_{12} & \bar{S}_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \bar{S}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \tau_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Using the material values E_{glass} , ν_{glass} , $E_{\text{polyester}}$, and the densities shown in Table 2, the engineering constants defined in equation (5) are obtained using the various rules as follows:

$-E_1$ is calculated using the rule of mixture

$$E_1 = E_g V_g + E_r V_r \quad (7)$$

where V_g and V_r are the volume fraction of fiber and resin respectively.

$-\nu_{12}$ is calculated using the rule of mixture

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_g V_g + \nu_r V_r \quad (8)$$

$-E_2$ is calculated using the Halpin-Tsai equations [5]

$$\frac{E_2}{E_r} = \frac{1 + \xi \eta V_g}{1 - \eta V_g} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } \eta = \frac{(E_g/E_r) - 1}{(E_g/E_r) + \xi} \quad (10)$$

and $\xi = 2$

- G_{12} is calculated using the Halpin equations similar to (9) and (10) with G_{12} replacing E_2 , G_r replacing E_r and with $\xi = 1$.

Values of the engineering constants as calculated are shown in Table 2.

Values of S_{11} , S_{12} , S_{22} and S_{66} are calculated using equation (5). These values are then substituted into equation (4) to obtain \bar{S}_{11} , \bar{S}_{12} , \bar{S}_{22} , \bar{S}_{66} in terms of θ . Using equations (6), (1) and (2), the direct strains are obtained to be:

$$\epsilon_x = \bar{S}_{11} \frac{PF}{2t} + \bar{S}_{12} \frac{PF}{t} \quad (11)$$

$$\epsilon_y = \bar{S}_{12} \frac{PF}{2t} + \bar{S}_{22} \frac{PF}{t} \quad (12)$$

For $\theta = 54.7^\circ$, equations (11) and (12) can be written as:

$$\epsilon_x = 110p \quad (13)$$

$$\epsilon_y = 1130p \quad (14)$$

Static Weight

Referring to Figures 1 and 2 and using bending theory, the material at the location of the gages are under a compressive stress of $\sigma_x = -0.444$ MPa. Substituting this value into equation (3) yields values of

$$\epsilon_x = -73 \times 10^{-6} \text{ and } \epsilon_y = 26 \times 10^{-6}$$

Total Strain and Comparison of Results:

The total strain would be the strains resulting from both loadings:

$$\epsilon_x = 110p - 73 \times 10^{-6} \quad (15)$$

$$\epsilon_y = 1130p + 26 \times 10^{-6} \quad (16)$$

Equations (15) and (16) are plotted as the solid lines in Figure 3. It can be seen that reasonable agreement is obtained between theoretical and experimental results.

OPTIMAL WINDING ANGLE FOR STRAIN LIMITED DESIGN

From the expression of the strains, it is clear that even though a winding angle of 54.7° gives a stress ratio of $\sigma_y/\sigma_x = 2$, the ratio between the strains $\epsilon_y/\epsilon_x = 10$. For strain limited designs, the winding angle of 54.7° may not be efficient.

In an effort to determine the optimal winding angle for strain limited designs, let x and y denote the longitudinal and hoop directions and 1 and 2 denote the directions along the fiber and perpendicular to the fiber respectively (Figure 4). The transformation of strains can be written as [6]:

$$\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_x \cos^2\theta + \epsilon_y \sin^2\theta + \gamma_{xy} \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad (17)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_x \sin^2\theta + \epsilon_y \cos^2\theta - \gamma_{xy} \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad (18)$$

Since there is no shear stress in cylindrical vessel, $\gamma_{xy} = 0$ and we have

$$\epsilon_1 = \epsilon_x \cos^2\theta + \epsilon_y \sin^2\theta \quad (19)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_x \sin^2\theta + \epsilon_y \cos^2\theta \quad (20)$$

using equations (11) and (12), equations (19), (20) can be written as:

$$\epsilon_1 = \frac{Pr}{2t} (\bar{S}_{11}\cos^2\theta + 2\bar{S}_{12}\sin^2\theta) \quad (21)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = \frac{Pr}{2t} (\bar{S}_{12}\sin^2\theta + 2\bar{S}_{22}\cos^2\theta) \quad (22)$$

Fig. 5: Variation of Strains with Winding Angle - CPF Vessel

Fig. 6: Variation of Strain with Winding Angle - Property Combination I

Using the values given in Table 2, values of ϵ_x , ϵ_y , ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 are plotted versus the winding angle θ as shown in Figure 5. It can be seen that ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 have the same values at $\theta = 45^\circ$ and also at $\theta = 70^\circ$. At $\theta = 70^\circ$, $\epsilon_x = \epsilon_y = \epsilon_1 = \epsilon_2$

and therefore this is the angle where strain is the same in all directions. Experimental work is being carried out to determine the benefits of the winding angle $\theta = 70^\circ$.

Fig 7: Variation of Strain with Winding Angle - Property Combination II

In general, the material properties are not the same as those given in Table 2, possible optimal angles for different combinations of material properties are shown in Figures 6 through 9. Figure 6 shows the variation of ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 with the winding angle θ for $E_1 = 72$ GPa, $E_2 = 3.6$ GPa, $G_{12} = 3.6$ GPa and $\nu_{12} = 0.2$. It can be seen that the two strains are about the same for range of angles from 45° to 56° . Similar range of angle is also seen in Figure 7. In Figure 8, a different property combination makes the optimal angles to be 45° and 75.5° . Figure 9 shows the angle ranges at which the two strains differ by less than 2% for different material properties. It can be seen that at $E_1 = 72$ GPa, $E_2 = 7.2$ GPa, the variation of ν_{12} does not affect the optimal angle significantly. For $G_{12}/E_1 = 0.3$, the variation of G_{12} does not affect much effect either.

CONCLUSION

Laminate theory was successfully used in calculating the strains in a fiber glass reinforced plastic cylindrical vessel subjected to internal pressure up to 0.96 MPa. For a winding angle of 54.7° , the ratio of hoop strength and longitudinal strength is 2 but the ratio of hoop strain and longitudinal strain is very large. This strain ratio depends on the material properties and can go up to the order of 10 or 100. Optimal angle can be determined so that the ratio of strains along different directions is minimum. The use of the optimal angle can lead to more efficient strain limited designs.

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Fig 8: Variation of Strain with Winding Angle - Property Combination III

Fig 9 : Variation of Optimal Winding Angle with Properties

Table 1: Strain values (10^{-6}) at different pressures

Loading Conditions	Gage	
	21 H	22 A
Empty	0	0
Full water	- 53	- 51
0.07 MPa (10 psi)	39	- 51
0.21 MPa (30 psi)	177	- 44
0.48 MPa (70 psi)	505	- 25
0.58 MPa (84 psi)	627	- 20
0.68 MPa (98 psi)	731	- 16
0.77 MPa (112 psi)	868	- 17
0.87 MPa (126 psi)	980	- 10
0.96 MPa (140 psi)	1146	0

$E_g = E_{\text{glass}} = 72 \text{ GPa} (10.5 \times 10^4 \text{ psi})$
 $\nu_g = 0.20$
 $E_r = E_{\text{polyester}} = 3.5 \text{ GPa} (0.51 \times 10^6 \text{ psi})$
 $\nu_r = 0.35$
 $d_g = 2.54; d_r = 1.02; \text{glass content} = 68\% \text{ by weight}$
 $E_1 = 65.6 \text{ GPa}$
 $\nu_{12} = 0.281$
 $E_2 = 10.4 \text{ GPa}$
 $G_{12} = 3.0 \text{ GPa}$

Table 2: Material constants